

The background of the slide is a vibrant, colorful landscape. The top half shows a rocky, multi-colored terrain with patches of blue, purple, and orange. The bottom half shows a bright blue, sandy beach with a person in a red shirt walking along the shore carrying a surfboard. A large, semi-transparent purple oval is overlaid on the left side of the image, containing the text.

Transformation Action Workshop I

Milestone 2

Transformation Dynamics

Technical References

Project Acronym	BioValue
Project Full Name	Biodiversity value in Spatial Planning Leveraging Multi-Level and Transformative Change
Project ID	101060790
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Lead Partner	IST
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Executive Summary

Despite international and European policies in place to halt biodiversity loss, the effect of multi-level, and multi-sector, direct and indirect drivers of change contribute to continuing negative trends. As biodiversity is impacted by many different sectors, the main challenge consists in balancing a wide range of interests and value systems across different political levels, negotiating different interests while ultimately seeking to improve, or at least maintain, biodiversity.

The main goal of BioValue is to safeguard and enhance biodiversity through transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development, upscaling opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of EU strategic actions on biodiversity, in particular the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. To address this, BioValue adopts three complementary instrumental perspectives relevant to spatial planning processes: spatial planning and management instruments (SP&MI), environmental assessment instruments (EAI), and economic and financial instruments (E&FI).

The instrumental perspectives will support the structuring of the research in three case studies (in Portugal, Italy, and Germany) to explore and experiment BioValue research frameworks with stakeholders in action. The case studies will work as arenas for transformation (arenas4transf), as 'experimental' areas of the capacity of the three instruments to create transformative change for biodiversity value enhancement. These cases represent distinct spatial planning systems and cultures, as well as for scale and biodiversity-related situations.

This report **delivers the results of the 1st Transformation Action Workshop (TAW)** that had the objective of a first understanding and exploration of the arenas4transf processes of transition, and its dynamics, supported by BioValue.

The TAWs are a series of spaces of collective thinking to co-create action-oriented knowledge and transformative pathways throughout the arena4transf processes. Specific objectives of the TAWs are:

- i. Support the structure of the transformation processes of the arenas4transf
- ii. Formulate needs and opportunities
- iii. Help co-creation and discussion among the arenas4transf
- iv. Facilitate knowledge brokerage between the arenas4transf
- v. Advance improvements for transformation of joint application of the three instrumental perspectives

Three more TAWs are expected to occur, in BioValue months 15 (in Italy), 23 (in Germany), and 30 (in Portugal).

The TAW I report constitutes BioValue Milestone 2 and it is a project public resource.

Reflection of the mapped dynamics – e.g., of questions for reflection

- a) What stands out? What does it mean?
- b) What are common or similar elements?
- c) Reflect on what deserves more attention based on your expected outcome
- d) Main conclusions and reflections of the TAW

Transformation Action Workshop I

[understand and explore the arenas4transf transition processes and its dynamics supported by BioValue]

TAW I

Objectives

Specific objectives:

- Identification of current activities, interventions and practices that impact biodiversity
- Outline considering subsystems and what needs to be phased in and out, and how this change can be supported
- Identify the current state in transition process
- Test and learn about the X-Curve visual tool for replication purposes.

Timing & Location:

March 7th 2023 from 9:00 to 12:30 (CEST), Aalborg University, Copenhagen, Denmark

Description:

This workshop takes the form of a discussion within each arena4transf context in order to map the dynamics of the local system aimed at change and worked as the first step of the arenas4transf to prioritise interventions addressing transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructures development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity.

It also worked as a testing momentum for the workshop approach, and to capacitate the arenas4transf partners to learn about the workshop approach and be able to replicate it in their contexts.

Background information – Initial expected outcomes

MV

Observe and facilitate mainstreaming of biodiversity in rewetting as a policy option for the **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern** (MV) under the Climate Act. Consider the multi-level aspects of planning while bringing together different actors from different sectors of society in the co-creation of the desirable future of the peatlands.

MAFRA

Promote a planning system in **Mafra** that is focused on protecting and valuing biodiversity and natural values beyond current legislations/regulations, while recognizing the high touristic pressure. Consider natural heritage, ecological structure and green infrastructure in the next planning cycle.

FERSINA RIVER

Promote a planning system that incorporates the principles of ecological transition into the **Fersina River**, while recognizing the diversity of territorial characteristics. Support the development of a coding system to include the protection of biodiversity into territorial development.

TAW I Structure

purpose: Use of the X-Curve¹ as the support tool to map the dynamics of the system and to *talk about change*

duration: 3h30min

activities:

- 1: Identification of activities, interventions and practices that impact biodiversity (arena) ~2h
- 2: Reflection of the mapped dynamics (plenary) ~45min
- 3: How to move forward – replication of the workshop (arena) ~15min

TAW I

Structure

activity 1: identification of activities, interventions and practices that impact biodiversity

Based on the arenas4transf expected outcome, reflect on the dynamics of the system that you recognize the existence or see in your arena – e.g., activities/practices, resources, actors. Make sure the focus is on observed activities/practices and not possible (future) interventions

- What needs to be organized/changed/adapted/modified?
- What needs to be built/developed?
- What is the end goal?
- What stands out? What does it mean?

activity 2: reflection of the mapped dynamics

Overall discussion considering the arenas4transf results:

- What are common or similar elements?
- What deserves more attention based on the arenas4transf expected outcome?

activity 3: how to move forward

- What deserves more attention based on the arenas4transf expected outcome?
- How can we replicate this workshop in our contexts?

TAW I Structure - workgroups -

MV

- Arena MV representative I
- Arena MV representative II (*online*)
- WP1 representative
- WP3 representative (*online*)
- WP4 representative

MAFRA

- Arena Mafra representative I
- Arena Mafra representative II
- WP1 representative
- WP3 representative

FERSINA RIVER

- Arena Fersina River representative I
- Arena Fersina River representative II
- WP1 representative
- WP2 representative
- WP3 representative

TAW I
Results
- MV -

EXPECTED
OUTCOME

Observe and facilitate mainstreaming of biodiversity in rewetting as a policy option for the **Mecklenburg-Vorpommern** (MV) under the Climate Act. Consider the multi-level aspects of planning while bringing together different actors from different sectors of society in the co-creation of the desirable future of the peatlands.

MAPPED DYNAMICS X-CURVE

TAW I Results - Mafra -

REVISED EXPECTED
OUTCOME

Promote a planning system in **Mafra** that is focused on protecting and valuing biodiversity and nature beyond current legislations/regulations of the municipal ecological structure, while recognizing the high touristic pressure. Consider natural capital in the green infrastructure in the next planning cycle – built green infrastructure to adapt to the high touristic pressure.

MAPPED DYNAMICS X-CURVE

TAW I Results - Fersina River -

REVISED EXPECTED
OUTCOME

Promote a planning system that incorporates the principles of ecological transition in the **Fersina River**, while recognizing the diversity of spatial characteristics. Support the development of a coding system that incorporates biodiversity protection into spatial development by focusing on developing an intervention project on the Fersina River as a pilot project that integrates the implementation of biodiversity protection policies

MAPPED DYNAMICS X-CURVE

TAW I Results - Reflections & questions per arena4transf -

activity 1: identification of activities, interventions and practices that impact biodiversity

MV:

- Find prioritisation areas for rewetting where negative impact is low.
- Bringing together actors with different knowledge (e.g., moor center, farmers, ...).
- Bridging sectoral thinking and planning.
- Market for Schwarzerle (land wood from peat soils).
- Explore potential avenues for paludiculture (within the Common Agricultural policy - CAP)
- Initiatives to maintain measures under Aktionsprogramm Natürlicher Klimaschutz (ANK).
- Options to integrate wind and solar energy.
- Farmers as key actors: finding co-benefits for agrifood system.
- Are there any actions that could/should be taken to enhance benefits of rewetting for biodiversity? Can rewetting be made in a 'nature-positive' way?
- How much can the federal state influence CAP funding pro/con peat soil rewetting?

Mafra:

- Vision for the future: The Green Finger Plan (built green infrastructure to adapt to the high touristic pressure) – to be confirmed/discussed in Mafra workshop.
- Need for citizens (landowners) to recognize the full value (economic and environment of green infrastructure).
- Spatial planning dynamics cannot keep pace with changing situations.
- Definition of "quality of life" and recognition of the value of land should be consistent between public and private actors.

Fersina River:

- Sense of place/belonging: more spaces for deliberation to raise people's awareness need to be created/developed. Also, connection of people with the river is restricted by current regulations.
- There are a lot of tools not making real impact. Exist to exist, are not being used.
- Promote a less strict regulation (water banks accessibility).
- Need for more flexible legislation? To promote relations p.e.
- How to cope with the competition of functions in the area of the river? E.g., Establishment of strategies to deal with the high land use competition.
- Establish options to decrease urban inequality (bypass).
- Analyze new developments (e.g., infrastructure, scientific tools) and their potentiality (new hospital Trento, touristic routes- University, TUT biodiversity values)
- Integrate different initiatives and projects: PUMS sustainable mobility, underground railway project (recovery found bypass), identity connection with the river.
- As next step: promote and raise awareness to change local perceptions (e.g., for car use).

TAW I Results - Global -

TAW I

Results

- Global -

There were **six main aspects** that were mentioned by the three arenas, and the main message can be expressed as:

- **Perceptions:** importance of understanding the different perceptions at stake, working towards change in promoting shared thinking about the importance of biodiversity for territorial development and spatial planning systems.
- **Regulations:** current regulations are restrictive in nature and may not be expressing, in a positive way, different policy options for spatial transformation that cope with biodiversity and nature. There is the need to overcome current practices of 'working in silos' and to promote cross-sectoral approaches.
- **Ownership:** Is important to shift from thinking of biodiversity and natural capital as restrictive in a way for policymakers/landowners to take ownership of their territories and thus recognize the possible uses of valued biodiversity.
- **Governance:** governance systems need to promote relational approaches in order to promote cooperation and collaboration among different decision-making levels.
- **Awareness:** more needs to be done to raise awareness on biodiversity and nature, in order to, in a positive and informed way, consider/integrate biodiversity value in spatial planning policies and more local practices.
- **Valuation:** overall recognition that 'green does not have an economic value' and does not 'represent development', and the importance of overcoming current perceptions to recognize value in all of its dimensions (economic, social and natural).

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